

Motor Imagery Based Brain Computer Interface

Undergraduate graduation project report submitted in partial fulfilment of
the requirements for the
Degree of Bachelor of Science of Engineering
in

The Department of Electronic & Telecommunication Engineering
University of Moratuwa.

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DECLARATION

This declaration is made on January 24, 2017.

Declaration by Project Group

We declare that the dissertation entitled Motor Imagery Based Brain Computer Interface and the work presented in it are our own. We confirm that:

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ABSTRACT

Motor Imagery Based brain computer interface

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Keywords: Brain Computer Interface, motor imagery, classification, EEG, Wavelet Packet Decomposition, Neighbourhood Component Analysis, Neural Network

In this final year project report detailed outline of a motor imagery based brain computer interface is provided. This project focused on discovering ways to establish an accurate brain computer interface (BCI) to detect an individual's left and right upper limb motor imagery using EEG signals obtained from a wearable EEG head cap and a EEG acquisition system. In the phase 1 of this project, an artificial neural network with 3 layers was used to reach the above objective resulting in a maximum accuracy of 71% and an average accuracy of 65%. In this phase we propose a BCI implemented using Wavelet Packet Decomposition for feature extraction and Neighborhood Component Analysis for feature selection while classification is done using a 3-layer Neural Network. This proposed methodology recorded a maximum accuracy of 82.9% and an average accuracy of 79.6% for the data acquired using ADInstruments Power Lab together with ECI cap. This method was seen to fully classify signals acquired using g.EEGsys EEG acquisition system, which needs further validation. According to the results of the analysis done during this project, we conclude the accuracy of proposed BCI platform directly depends upon the subject, the level of concentration of the subject on the task, the methods used to establish the BCI platform, quality of acquired signal the size of the training set used in training the classifier.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Our heartfelt gratitude is extended to the supervisor of our project, Dr. Anjula De Silva for the immense support and encouragement given to initiate and carry out this project. His perfect guidance and strength given at times we were in need as well as appreciations in our achievements are the foundation of the successful completion of this project.

We thank Dr. Upeka Premaratne for the valuable insight and guidance given with genuine interest.

We Thank Dr. Thilina Lalitharatne, Department of Mechanical Engineering for allowing us to use g.EEGsys EEG acquisition system for our data acquisition purposes.

Our gratitude is also extended to all the staff members of the Department of Electronic and Telecommunication Engineering.

Last but not least we extend our thanks to all the academic as well as non-academic staff members of University of Moratuwa and our fellow batch mates for the support and motivation provided throughout the project.

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

BCI	–	Brain Computer Interface
EEG	–	Electroencephalogram
MI	–	motor imagery
NN	–	Neural Network
DNN	–	Deep Neural Network
FFT	–	Fast Fourier Transform
EMG	–	Electromyogram
MRI	–	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
fMRI	–	functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
PCA	–	Principal Component Analysis
PSD	–	Power Spectral Density
DWT	–	Discrete Wavelet Transformation
WPD	–	Wavelet Packet Decomposition
NCA	–	Neighborhood Component Analysis
SVM	–	Support Vector Machine
LDA	–	Linear Discriminant Analysis

CHAPTER 1

1 INTRODUCTION

Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) build the platform to create a new paradigm in communication between humans and computers. They try to unveil the brain level information which may or may not be available to an individual's consciousness, by means of brain signal analysis. The successful harvesting of brain level information without involving muscular or vocal communication could lead the pathway to numerous technologies including mind controlled devices and computer applications, fine-tuned prosthetics, brain-to-brain communication and many more. Even though the initial intend of BCIs were for medical applications, today BCIs are also targeted for the general public – mostly in terms of entertainment and communication.

The acquisition of brain signals could either be invasive where the electrodes are surgically implanted into the brain or non-invasive where electrodes are placed on the scalp. The BCIs have two main categories; dependent BCIs and independent BCIs. Depending on the BCI requirement additional input of muscular activity (EMG) in addition to brain signals to identify a task while independent BCIs only require brain signal inputs. The most convenient source of obtaining brain signals for BCIs are electroencephalography (EEG) as EEG provides high temporal resolution at low cost even though there are other technologies like fMRI, SPECT and MEG. Currently there are three prominent approaches for the independent BCIs; P300, Steady State Visual Evoked Potential (SSVEP) and motor imagery. Out of these motor imagery based BCI has many promising applications in a wider range.

A motor imagery is a mental stimulation of a motor function by an individual. It is proven that motor imagery causes a temporal, spatial and frequency domain effect in brain signals acquired in the form of EEG. It is also proven that this behavior of EEG is subjective to the individual performing the task and the concentration on the task. An optimum motor

imagery based BCI targets to capture these behavioral changes in EEG and interpret it meaningfully irrespective of the subjectiveness of the EEG data.

In this project we sought to develop an accurate motor imagery based BCI to differentiate and detect the right and left hand motor imageries. This project is an extension of the brain-to-brain communication project carried out by a group of our senior biomedical engineering students.

1.1 Phase 1 Accomplishments

In the phase 1 of this project a BCI to classify right and left fist motor imagery was developed using a three layer neural network with 9 input features in the input layer, 25 neurons in the hidden layer and 2 labels in the output layer. The features based were extracted using wavelet transform. This designed BCI recorded a maximum accuracy of 71%.

1.2 Problem Statement

“Unveiling information in our brain which is not introspectively available to our consciousness is a challenging task due to the nature of EEG signals, noise and other artifacts. Therefore, there is a need of a robust and accurate BCI to be established. “

1.3 Objectives

Establish an accurate BCI by exploring mechanisms of signal processing and machine learning.

- Selecting the most appropriate data acquisition EEG electrode channels.
- Discover signal processing approaches to remove biological and non-biological artifacts and enhance EEG signals.
- Discover optimal features that contain motor imagery information.
- Discover optimal classifiers to identify motor imagery between left and right hand movements.

CHAPTER 2

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Biological Background

The brain consists of three major parts: cerebrum, cerebellum and brainstem. The short extension between spinal cortex and cerebral cortex and cerebellum is the brainstem. It is known as the integration center of motor reflexes. The conscious functions are handled by the cerebrum and cerebellum maintains the body muscle movement balance. [17][18]

Information like pain and touch are delivered to the brain stem through ascending nerve tracts originating from the spinal cord while the descending nerve tract connects the brain divisions to the motor neurons which control the activity of the skeletal muscles.

The imagination of a motor activity is considered as mental rehearsal of motor act. It involves the same brain regions as the physical motor activity [16]. These motor movements are planned in the basal ganglia, the cortex and the lateral portion of the cerebellar hemisphere, therefore the electrical activity in these regions get highly increased before the movement. The motor cortex and premotor cortex (figure 2) receive the information through thalamus and then passes that motor information to the spinal cord through the corticobulbar tracts and corticospinal tracts to the motor brain stem's motor neurons [17].

It has been found that the primary motor cortex which is located in the precentral gyrus as shown in figure 2 is involved in voluntary movement. Most of the body postures, movements are projected on this area such as tongue, hand and feet body movement on the top of the gyrus. The disproportionate map of the body in motor cortex is illustrated on figure 1. The functionality of the premotor cortex is involved in setting posture at the beginning of a planned movement and it is still not fully understood [17].

Figure 2.1 Primary motor cortex

Figure 2.2 Major areas of human brain

The Brain's electrical activity is usually recorded using three modalities [19].

1. Scalp electrodes that allow a non-invasive recording of the brain electrical activity.
2. Cortical electrodes that are placed on the cortex of the brain. This recording is called Electrocorticography (ECoG) which is an invasive approach.
3. Depth recording, which is also an invasive method that requires inserting needle electrodes into the brain.

In brain computer interfaces the non-invasive method is preferred. The electrical potentials which is recorded from the brain is a superposition of all the electrical activities from all the neurons. However a better spatial resolution and also a higher signal to noise ratio can be obtained by being closer to the source of activity.

The international 10-20 system of electrode placement was introduced to standardize the placement of the electrodes for all the subjects (figure 3). Bipolar Montage refers to measuring the difference between two adjacent electrodes. The referential montage describes the measurement with respect to a reference electrode [19].

Figure 2.3 The international 10-20 system

2.2 Brain Computer Interface

Alireza Ghaemi et al (2016) in the paper ‘Automatic channel selection in EEG signals for classification of left or right hand movement in Brain Computer Interfaces using improved binary gravitation search algorithm’ [1], have applied logarithmic power of each channel computed in the time domain and the features of mean, mode, median, variance, and standard deviation in the wavelet domain as features. This method involves support vector machine (SVM) based classifier. The main concentration of the research is directed towards automatic detection of optimum channels to achieve better classification results. To this purpose improved binary gravitation search algorithm (IBGSA) is used. In addition this paper reflects that the accuracy of classification is subjective of the person. This methodology has shown a maximum accuracy of 80% and average accuracy of 76.24% for the datasets from eight subjects.

In the study of ‘Comparison of signal decomposition methods in classification of EEG signals for motor-imagery BCI system’ [2] by Jasmin Kevric and Abdulhamid Subasi [2016], Empirical Mode Decomposition, Discrete Wavelet Transform, and Wavelet Packet Decomposition have been investigated for their performance in motor imagery classification using K-nearest neighbor (K-NN) classifier. EEG signal is acquired from C3, C4 and CZ channels covering the motor cortex. In this study, the highest classification

accuracy of 92.8% is achieved for the combination of Multiscale Principal Component Analysis (MSPCA) de-noising and higher order statistics features extracted from wavelet packet decomposition sub-bands.

The following tables (table 1, table 2, table 3) show the accuracies for the 3 decomposition methods of the 5 subjects who participated. The EXP1, EXP2, EXP3 are carried out using different combinations of the statistical features extracted.

Table 2.1 Classification accuracy for different feature sets

Classification Accuracy using EMD.

	AA	AL	AV	AW	AY	ALL
EXP1	54.0	56.1	49.4	55.1	75.3	58.2
EXP2	59.8	59.7	57.9	54.1	88.4	62.4
EXP3	56.6	60.7	55.9	55.1	90.1	62.8

Classification Accuracy using DWT.

	AA	AL	AV	AW	AY	ALL
EXP1	62.7	65.7	61.1	59.8	67.0	64.7
EXP2	80.7	76.1	76.3	86.3	86.0	82.0
EXP3	77.1	72.2	75.2	85.6	86.0	81.1

Classification Accuracy using 4 level WPD.

	AA	AL	AV	AW	AY	ALL
EXP1	83.0	81.4	78.4	85.3	75.4	82.6
EXP2	96.0	92.0	88.3	95.4	91.4	93.7
EXP3	94.8	92.3	88.9	94.7	91.1	94.5

Jyoti et al [3] proposes a multi-channel EEG processing methodology by dividing all electrodes according to their placement in these brain lobes among five major regions; frontal region channels, central region channels, temporal region channels, parietal region channels and occipital region channels and extract features for each region using stationary common spatial patterns (SCSP) technique. This study utilizes a composite kernel support vector machine for the classification. This study depicts that the use of an anatomically

based spatial filter can enhance the performance of a brain computer interface. The training and performance evaluation method of this study is shown below in figure 4.

Figure 2.4 Outline of training and testing phase of the proposed method

Table 2.2 Comparison of classification accuracies

Comparison of classification Accuracy for Dataset 1.

Subject	CSP	SCSP	CKSCSP at $\mu = 0$	CKSCSP at $\mu \neq 0$
aa	75.37	80.45	80.01	81.14
al	97.73	94.38	98.04	98.34
av	69.14	69.82	70.25	77.56
aw	82.27	82.43	86.63	86.64
ay	82.17	89.33	87.83	88.17
Mean	81.33	83.28	84.55	86.37

Comparison of classification Accuracy for Dataset 2.

Subject	CSP	SCSP	CKSCSP at $\mu_{R_1} = 0$	CKSCSP at $\mu_{R_1} \neq 0$
ds1a	73.10	81.75	62.60	67.05
ds1b	65.40	59.95	65.35	71.45
ds1c	70.50	75.1	73.05	75.35
ds1d	76.80	89.2	87.30	90.3
ds1e	83.30	90.35	89.70	89.55
ds1f	82.80	86.9	84.40	88.3
ds1g	79.00	91.45	92.45	94.75
Mean	75.84	82.1	79.26	82.39

The above tables (table 4 and table 5) lists the accuracy comparison of the method proposed in [3] and other existing methods. This data also suggests that the BCI accuracy is subjective to the person.

The figures below show the selected anatomical brain regions using the spatial filter for the different subjects. This depicts that the spatial behavior of EEG is also subject dependent.

Figure 2.5 selected anatomical brain regions using the spatial filter for the different subjects

Hari et al [2016] in their study ‘Classification of EEG Motor imagery multi class signals based on Cross Correlation’ [4] have suggested extracting statistical features; mean, median, mode, standard deviation, maximum and minimum based on cross correlation (CC) technique. They have used five different classifiers and selected the best classifier based on a voting method. This method has shown 29.82% improvement in Kappa values relative to already existing approaches.

In the ‘Detection of motor imagery EEG signals employing Naïve Bayes based learning process’ [5], Siuly (2016) et al proposes Naïve Bayes classification using Optimum Allocation (OA) based feature extraction achieving average accuracy of 96.36%. The extracted features are mean, median, mode, standard deviation, maximum, minimum, first

quartile (Q1), third quartile (Q3) (75th percentile), inter-quartile range (IQR), skewness and kurtosis.

In the ‘Improvement of EEG-based motor imagery classification using ring topology-based particle swarm optimization’ [6] by Hamid et al (2016) proposes ring topology-based particle swarm optimization (RTPSO) algorithm for classifier tuning. Tuning of feed-forward neural network (FFNN) and three types of support vector machines are considered in the study. The results of this research states that this method outperforms BCI 2003 and 2005 competition winning methods.

Kai et al (2017) in ‘EEG-Based Strategies to Detect Motor Imagery for Control and Rehabilitation’ [13] introduce optimized spatial filters using the common spatial pattern (CSP) algorithm and a shrinkage-regularized linear discriminant analysis classifier for classification. A subject-specific

Filter bank common spatial pattern (FBCSP) algorithm is used in this method. It yields machine learning accuracy of 69.5%.

‘Motor Imagery based Brain Computer Interface using Transform Domain Features’ [14] by Ahmad et al (2016) develops a BCI utilizing three EEG channels; C3, C4, CZ. Magnitude of the discrete Fourier transform (DFT), the discrete wavelet transform (DWT) coefficients (Daubechies 4 (db4) family, Ca3, Cd3, Cd2, Cd1), distance series (DS) values, and invariant moments are extracted as features and principal component analysis (PCA) is employed for feature selection. Selected sets of features are analyzed with K-nearest neighbor (KNN), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA) and support vector machine (SVM) with linear kernel classifiers. This study has shown the following accuracies for the following combinations of feature sets and classifiers.

- Magnitude of FFT - KNN K=7 - 89.28%
- Coefficients of DWT – QDA - 87.14%
- DS of the RPS – LDA – 90.71%
- Invariant moments of the RPS - SVM with linear kernel - 87.85%

CHAPTER 3

3 METHODOLOGY

The general steps in a BCI implementation are; data acquisition, pre-processing, feature extraction, classification and evaluation.

Figure 3.1 Block diagram

3.1 Data Acquisition

The motor imagery information of an individual is acquired through scalp EEG. The EEG signal carrying motor imagery information has 2 main aspects,

- Temporal information
- Spatial information

Therefore when acquiring EEG signal, both these aspects should be captured. For signal acquisition 2 systems were used.

- AD Instruments Power Lab and ECI cap
- g.EEGsys EEG Research System

3.1.1 Signal Acquisition using AD Instruments Power Lab and ECI cap

ADInstruments EEG signal acquisition system we used for the data collection mainly have 3 parts; The ADInstruments octal bio amp, ADInstruments power lab 16/35 amp and the ECI electro head cap.

The main limitation when using AD Instruments Power Lab is the limitation in number of channels that can be acquired. A maximum of 8 channels can be acquired using AD Instruments Power Lab. Also the ECI cap has 21 channels according to 10-20 electrode placement system. Which limits the accessibility of some electrodes correlated with motor cortex. Considering these the channels for data selection was determined as shown in the below picture.

Figure 3.2 Electrode positions related to motor cortex

Figure 3.3 Selected electrodes from ECI cap electrode positions

The data acquisition is done using a matlab app which is integrated with Lab Chart data acquisition software. At the start of a trial this app allows a 5 Seconds relax time and shows a countdown of 5 Seconds. At the end of the 5 Seconds the app displays the task to perform, whether left or right and the subject performs the given task in the next 3 Seconds. The acquired signal is then saved in the .mat format.

Throughout the data acquisition process the input impedance between the channels were kept below 4 k Ω using Checktrode device.

The diagram below sums up the steps in the data acquisition process.

Figure 3.4 Block diagram of data acquisition process

Figure 3.5 Signal acquisition using ADInstruments system

Major components of ADInstruments EEG acquisition system are;

- ADInstruments Octal Bio Amp

The Octal Bio amp have high performance, galvanically isolated differential amplifiers which is specially optimized to measure a variety of Biological signals including EEG. It consists of a range of filter settings which improves the signal quality by improving signal to noise ratio. [29]

Figure 3.7 ADInstruments Octal Bio Amplifier

Figure 3.6 ADInstruments PowerLab 16/35 amplifier

- ADInstruments PowerLab 16/35

The ADInstrument PowerLab 16/35 is the most powerful amplifier in the series. It has 16 analog input channels and 4 can be used differential mode. It has 16 bit ADC resolution and maximum per channel sampling rate is 200kS/s. Each of the 16 channels have noise reduction circuitry and in build filters to reduce the signal noise and crosstalk. This amplifier can be linked with Lab Chart software in order to acquire data using a computer. [30]

- ECI Electro cap

For the data collection process we used ECI elctro cap large size which consists of Pb electrodes. As it has passive electrodes a good skin preparation needs to be done prior to the data collection. It consists of 19 EEG channels and we used eight electrode channels from international 10-20 EEG electrode placement method shown in figure 1.1.8 as input EEG channels. The chin straps and a body harness is used to fit the electro cap to the head correctly. [31]

Figure 3.8 ECI electro head cap

– Checktrode Model 1089ES

The Model 1089ES Checktrode® is used to test the integrity of electrode-skin contact in bio electrical data acquisition systems like EEG systems. It also can be used to measure voltages generated by electrodes separately and also to test integrity of electrode leads by measuring the impedance between the ground and the corresponding electrode. The ECI electro cap can be connected via DB-25 electrode cap connector (Figure 1.1.13) to this this device. Impedances of the electrodes are lowered by applying electro gel and measured manually by turning the switch to the following switch positions. As we used passive electrode the skin-electrode impedance was lowered below $4k\Omega$.

Figure 3.9 Checktrode 1089ES model

Figure 3.10 Checktrode connector to ECI electro cap

Integration of ADInstrument Lab chart SDK with Matlab

The ADInstrument Lab chart SDK was implemented using Matlab to perform data collection. The callback functions of the GUI was coded to implement the methods of ADInstruments Lab chart.

3.1.2 Signal Acquisition using g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System

Figure 3.11 g.BCIsys BCI research system

Figure 3.12 Data collection using g.BCIsys

A complete Matlab based research and development system is provided by g.tec which includes all the hardware and software components required for the signal acquisition. With the provided Matlab Simulink software package it enables high speed online processing and reading of bio signal data directly into Simulink models. There are Simulink models to visualize data and also to analyze data. g.BCIsys is a well-known data acquisition system used in developing brain computer interfaces. [28]

The motor cortex spans in the central region of the brain approximately starting from one ear to another. The channels around C4 electrode corresponds to the movement or motor imagery of left hand and channels around C3 corresponds to the movement or motor imagery of right hand. Therefore electrodes were positioned to cover all the electrode positions corresponds to motor imagery in the 10-20 system. Some extra electrode positions were used because EEG head-caps never positions perfectly to the point. Standard reference and ground electrodes positions of g.BCIsys head-cap were used as reference and ground electrodes respectively. [31]

Main components of g.EEGsys EEG acquisition system are,

- Electrode head-cap

g.EEGsys has several electrode head caps which contains 32 and 64 channel electrodes from 3 different sizes; small, large, medium. We used 64 channel medium size electrode head cap for our data collection procedure. It contains Ag/AgCl electrodes which can capture the evoke potentials accurately. It has active

electrode which consists of inbuilt pre-amps that reduce the noise. After usage, the head cap needs to be washed and cleaned. [28]

Figure 3.14 g.BCIsys head-cap

Figure 3.13 g.HIamp

– G.HIamp

g.HIamp is an FDA cleared and CE approved 256 channel biosignal amplifier which can be used to non-invasive and invasive signal measurements of brain's function. It has 256 ADC converters with an ADC resolution of 24 bits which gives a wide range of sensitivity to measure biosignals without getting saturated. All the channels are DC coupled and amplifier works in a very high sampling frequency in order to reduce the noise by averaging samples. The amplifier is connected to the computer using USB and it is powered using medical mains power supply. All the 64 channels of the EEG headcap can be connected to the electrode interface box via multi-pole medical safety connectors. Novel floating point DSP is used inside the amp and all the 256 channels can be analyzed using the Simulink toolbox in real-time. [32]

In default mode the sampling rate is 256 Hz but we used a sampling rate of 1200Hz in order to have a good signal resolution. The DSP performs the band pass filtering of each channel between 0.5 and 100 Hz. In addition to that a mains notch filter of (50/60 Hz) can be applied to cut off the power line interferences. Then the signal sent to the computer through USB.

When calibrating g.Hiamp every input pin is shorted and an internally generated square wave pulse (amplitude ± 7.5 mV and 10 Hz) is applied as the input of the amplifier. Then the input impedance of the electrodes should be lowered in order to get a quality signal. We used active electrodes and therefore it needs a less skin preparation. Electrode impedance below $30\text{k}\Omega$ was maintained to get signals with lesser artifacts. When the impedance measurement wizard is opened and internally generated square wave is supplied on the signal ground connector and all the electrodes are connected to the subject's body. The transmission of signal is evaluated in order to calculate the impedance measurements. [32]

Figure 3.15 Impedance measurement GUI of g.BCI sys

Integration of G.Hiamp HA with Matlab

The g.Hiamp HA Simulink block feeds raw data to the Simulink entity. That data was unbuffered and data type is converted to double and sent to the workspace. Then the raw data was recoded to a Matlab file according to the data acquisition protocol using data acquisition GUI.

Measuring biosignal data

In measuring mode, all input channels are amplified and each channel is sampled with a 24 bit analog to digital converter. In default mode the sampling rate is 256 Hz. The DSP performs the bandpass filtering of each channel between 0.5 and 100 Hz. Additionally a corresponding mains frequency notch filter (50/60 Hz) can be applied. Then the signal is transmitted via USB to the PC.

Calibrating g.HIamp

In calibration mode all input sockets must be shorted and the internally generated square wave of amplitude ± 7.5 mV and 10 Hz is applied to the input amplifiers.

Impedance measurement

In impedance measurement mode all electrodes are connected to the amplifier and to the subject's body. The internally generated square wave (± 7.5 mV) is supplied on the signal ground connector. The signal transmission can be evaluated to calculate the electrode impedance at 10 Hz.

HOLD of inputs

A TTL high impulse on the HOLD (signal constant) input socket can be used to hold the current signal on a constant level as long as the TTL impulse is set to high.

3.1.3 Data acquisition protocol

- The EEG recording process was conducted in a closed, noise free rooms. (Department of ENTC, Mechanical Engineering laboratories)
- Two healthy men participated as subjects in this work
- The age range of the participated subjects was between 24 to 25 years old
- Subjects should have slept at least six hours in the night, the day before the experiment was conducted and should be medication free.
- During the experiment, subjects need to perform two different imaginary tasks.

- I. Right hand movement
- II. Left hand movement
- III. During the experiment the subject was given relaxation period of 5 seconds. Then the subjects were requested to imagine that they were making left or right forearm movements for 3 seconds, according to the instruction given by the GUI. (Figure 3.16)

3.1.4 Graphical User Interfaces used for data collection

When the data acquisition starts it indicated 5 seconds and counts down to zero giving time for the relaxation of the subject. Then it randomly generates a clue (Left or Right) as depicted in the GUI phase 2. It prevails for 3 seconds and stops the recording. The 8 seconds length EEG recording is saved as a '.mat' file along with the clue.

Figure 3.16 Graphical User Interface, phase 1

Figure 3.17 Graphical User Interface, phase 2

3.1.5 Data Acquisition Sessions

There were 13 EEG acquisition sessions performing two tasks; the motor imagery (MI) task and Alpha state relaxation. The data was taken from 2 subjects inside two laboratories situated in University of Moratuwa. Mainly the data was acquired during the evening time and night time. The database information are given in the table

Table 3.1 Data acquisition sessions

Data Set	Date Acquired	Instrument	Task	Subject	Location	Time	No. of Trials	Sampling Frequency
1	2017.07.14	ADIns	MI	U	Opto Lab	Eve	104	1000
2	2017.07.26	ADIns	MI	U	Opto Lab	Eve	55	1000

3	2017.08.05	ADIns	MI	U	Opto Lab	Eve	100	1000
4	2017.09.07	ADIns	MI	U	Opto Lab	Eve	201	1000
5	2018.01.12	ADIns	MI	U	Mech	Aft	200	1000
6	2018.01.17	ADIns	MI	S	Telecom Lab	Aft	200	1000
7	2018.01.18	ADIns	MI	U	Opto Lab	Aft	405	1000
8	2018.11.05	g.EEGsys	MI	U	Mech	Aft	200	1200
9	2018.12.24	g.EEGsys	MI	H	Mech	Eve	100	1200
10	2018.12.26	g.EEGsys	MI	U	Mech	Eve	200	1200
11	2018.12.28	g.EEGsys	MI	U	Mech	Eve	200	1200
12	2017.10.22	ADIns	Alpha	U	Opto Lab	Aft	29	1000
13	2017.11.02	g.EEGsys	Alpha	U	Mech	Eve	20	1200

3.2 Pre-processing

The following standard pre-processing steps were followed mainly in this analysis.

Each trial data acquired using ADInstruments Power Lab contains 8 Second EEG data of 8 channels. A sampling frequency of 1000 Hz was used during signal acquisition, which resulted in 8000 samples per a single channel. Since the motor imagery was performed during the last 3 Seconds, the last 3 seconds of 8 channels is extracted. This reduces the signal to 3000 samples X 8 channels.

Whereas, trial data acquired using g,EEGsys EEG acquisition System contains 8 Second EEG data of 15 channels. A sampling frequency of 1200 Hz was used during signal acquisition, which resulted in 9600 samples per a single channel. Since the motor imagery

was performed during the last 3 Seconds, the last 3 seconds of 15 channels is extracted. This reduces the signal to 3600 samples X 15 channels.

These extracted signals are then,

- Band-pass filtered between 8 – 30 Hz frequency range
- Down sampled to 100Hz

3.2.1 Band-pass Filtering

The signal was band pass filtered in the Mu band (8 – 30 Hz) to filter out the signal of interest which carry motor imagery information. For this task a Butterworth IIR filter of order 20 was used.

Use of Butterworth Filter

As we are dealing with detecting motor imagery, we are interested in the getting the frequency response with minimum distortions. The frequency response of the Butterworth Filter approximation function is also often referred to as "maximally flat" (no ripples) response because the pass band is designed to have a frequency response which is as flat as mathematically possible in the cut-off frequency range. Therefore, this is the most suitable type of filter for our application.

Use of IIR filter

In this application we deal with bulk data. Therefore computational time of the filter is much important. Since IIR filters require fewer coefficients as to a FIR filter with similar characteristics, we selected IIR filter to carry out a faster and less memory consuming filtering.

Also Since in this application time alignment of signal components is not much critical as much as the amplitude response, the drawback of IIR filters –the non-linear phase response can be neglected. To avoid amplitude distortions, forward-backward filtering is not used.

Filter Parameters

The 3dB cut off frequencies of the band pass filter are FC1 and FC2, where FC1 = 8 Hz, FC2=30 Hz, The signal acquisition sampling rate, $F_s = 1200$ Hz or 1000 Hz (Which more than 10 times larger than the desired band, 220 Hz).

Selection of Filter Order

We used 'fdatool' of Matlab to generate this bandpass filter and used the minimal order (N=50) which is automatically created the filter design tool. It showed a clear filtered response in the frequency response but in the time domain around first 500 sample were zero. The reason for this is higher order IIR filters like Butterworth 50th order filters have considerably lengthy transient responses when compared with the length of its steady state response. The following figure show the frequency and time domain responses of the filtered signal.

Figure 3.18 Frequency spectrum and time domain signal after band pass filtering with minimum order filter generated by fdatool

In order to get rid of this unwanted transient data in the beginning, the time domain and frequency domain responses of the signal were monitored changing the order of the Butterworth filter. Filter orders were changed from 2 to 50. Some of the significant plots are shown below.

Figure 3.19 Frequency spectrum and time domain signal after band pass filtering with filter order 4

Figure 3.20 Frequency spectrum and time domain signal after band pass filtering with filter order 18

Figure 3.21 Frequency spectrum and time domain signal after band pass filtering with filter order 20

Figure 3.22 Frequency spectrum and time domain signal after band pass filtering with filter order 30

Considering the time and frequency domain representations, $N = 20$ was selected by visual inspection as the order of the Butterworth filter considering the tradeoff between transient response delay and filtering quality.

3.2.2 Down Sampling

Down sampling was done in order to reduce data points and to reduce the computational time. Down sampling done in accordance with Nyquist theory. The sampling frequency was reduced to 100 Hz which is more than twice the maximum signal frequency of 30 Hz.

- ADInstrument Power Lab
 - $F_s = 1000$ Hz
 - Down sample by a factor of 10 to obtain 100 Hz sampling frequency
- g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition system
 - $F_s = 1200$ Hz
 - Down sample by a factor of 12 to obtain 100 Hz sampling frequency

3.3 Feature Extraction

In this study, the following feature extraction methods were considered.

3.3.1 Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

The spectrum of a bio signal often contains essential information about the nature of the signal. Obtaining a spectrum from time series such as these involves the Fourier transform, and generalizations based on Fourier analysis. According to Fourier analysis any physical signal can be decomposed into a number of discrete frequencies, or a spectrum of frequencies over a continuous range. FFT samples a signal over a period of time and divides it into its frequency components.[20] The obtained components from FFT are single sinusoidal oscillations at distinct frequencies each with their own amplitude and phase.

Figure 3.23 Fourier transform: Divides a time-domain signal into its frequency components

The band pass filtered signal FFT is obtained channel wise and the absolute magnitude of the FFT data is fed to the system as classifier inputs.

The main drawback of this feature extraction approach is the loss of time information of the motor imagery signal.

3.3.2 Power Spectral Density (PSD)

The power spectrum of a time series describes the distribution of power into frequency components composing that signal.[25] The statistical average of a certain signal or sort of signal (including noise) as analysed in terms of its frequency content, is called its spectrum. The power spectral density (PSD), applies to signals existing over a time period large enough that it could as well have been over an infinite time interval. PSD then refers to the spectral energy distribution that would be found per unit time, since the total energy of such a signal over all time would generally be infinite.

The time series EEG signal involved in this study are directly measured using EEG electrodes, amplified by ADInstruments bioAmp and Power Lab and sampled using Lab Chart software application. The power spectrum is important in time-series signals typically when the process is a function of time, but one can similarly discuss data in the spatial domain being decomposed in terms of spatial frequency.[26]

The PSD of raw signals obtained from the most prominent 3 channels – C3, Cz and C4, are shown in the following figures.

Figure 3.24 Raw EEG signal of C3 channel and its PSD estimation

Figure 3.25 Raw EEG signal of Cz channel and its PSD estimation

Figure 3.26 Raw EEG signal of C4 channel and its PSD estimation

The PSD of pre-processed signals is shown in following figures.

Figure 3.27 Pre-processed signal of C3 channel and its PSD estimation

Figure 3.28 Pre-processed signal of Cz channel and its PSD estimation

Figure 3.29 Pre-processed signal of C4 channel and its PSD estimation

3.3.3 Epoch-wise Feature Extraction

The signal which consists of 300 samples for each channel is then segmented into 0.5 Seconds epochs having 50 samples. Then the epoch wise FFT or PSD is computed. As the basic features to the neural network, epoch wise magnitude of FFT or PSD is fed to the system as inputs.

3.3.4 Wavelet Packet Decomposition

Wavelet Packet Decomposition (WPD) aka Optimal Sub-band Tree Structuring (SB-TS) is a wavelet transform where the discrete-time (sampled) signal is passed through more filters than the discrete wavelet transform (DWT). In the DWT, each level is calculated by passing only the previous wavelet approximation coefficients (cA_j) through discrete-time low and high pass quadrature mirror filters.[21] However, in the WPD, both the detail (cD_j) and approximation coefficients are decomposed to create the full binary tree. [22] [23]

Figure 3.31 Discrete wavelet transform tree

Figure 3.30 Natural-ordered wavelet packet tree

For the WPD feature extraction Coiflet1 wavelet was used in this analysis since it is the highest correlated wavelet with EEG. [24] WPD analysis was done up to 5 levels and all level coefficients were extracted.

Figure 3.32 Coiflet1 wavelet

Figure 3.33 Time-frequency representation of C3, Cz and C4 channels

3.4 Feature Selection

3.4.1 Neighborhood Component Analysis (NCA)

Neighborhood component analysis (NCA) is a non-parametric and embedded method for selecting features with the goal of maximizing prediction accuracy of regression and classification algorithms. NCA algorithm performs NCA feature selection with regularization to learn feature weights for minimization of an objective function that measures the average leave-one-out classification or regression loss over the training data. [33]

NCA uses a randomized classifier as shown graphically in the figure. It adheres to following rules.

- Randomly picks a point, $\text{Ref}(x)$, from S as the ‘reference point’ for x
- Labels x using the label of the reference point $\text{Ref}(x)$.

Figure 3.34 Randomized classifier used for NCA

Then NCA computes Leave-one-out Probability of correct classification using the above mentioned randomized classifier as graphically shown in the following figure.

Figure 3.35 Computing leave-one-out probability of correct classification using randomized classifier

Accordingly, average LOO probability of correct classification is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(W) &= \sum P_i - \lambda \sum w_r^2 \\
 &= \sum F_i(w)
 \end{aligned}$$

The optimum feature weight vector w is selected in order to maximize the LOO probability of correct classification. This can be shown as the following minimization problem.

$$\hat{w} = \underset{w}{\operatorname{argmin}} f(w) = \sum a_i f_i(w)$$

Where,

$$f(w) = -F(w)$$

$$f_i(w) = -F_i(w)$$

Then by thresholding the obtained feature weight vector, the optimum features for classification can be selected by NCA.

3.5 Classification

After feature extraction and feature selection, the binary classification is performed using the selected features of the trials and their associated labels. Hence the classification problem is a supervised binary classification.

Classification was mainly done using 4 models.

- 3-layer Neural Network (NN)
- 4-layer Deep Neural Network (DNN)
- Support Vector Machine (SVM)
- Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)

3.5.1 3-layer Neural Network

For the classification, a 3 layer neural network is used with input layer size of number of FFT data input points, a hidden layer with 100 neurons and output layer having 2 labels.

Figure 3.36 Conventional neural network used for classification

3.5.2 4-layer Deep Neural Network

For the classification, a 4 layer deep neural network is used with input layer size of number of FFT data input points, hidden layer 1 with 100 neurons, hidden layer 2 with 25 neurons and output layer having 2 labels.

Figure 3.37 Deep neural network with 3 layers used for classification

3.5.3 Support Vector Machine

The used SVM model is shown below.

Figure 3.38 SVM Objective function model

3.5.4 Linear Discriminant Analysis

Classification using Linear Discriminant Analysis is shown below.

Figure 3.39 Linear discriminant analysis model

3.6 Proposed Methodology

3.6.1 Proposed Methodology Architecture

Based on our analysis and the results obtained for both signal acquisition systems, we propose a BCI implementation with 2 stages.

- Training stage

Initially for each subject the BCI should be trained using signal-clue set not less than 200 trials. During the initial training data set acquisition the subject should be fully relaxed and followed several practical training sessions in the data acquisition protocol and motor imagery task performance.

These obtained trial set is then used to extract wavelet features following to the standard pre-processing procedures. Using NCA the most relevant features for the

classification are selected and the corresponding indices are saved. Then the designed 3-layer neural network is trained using the selected features and the network parameters are obtained.

– Prediction Stage

In the prediction stage the trained BCI is used to classify each trial the subject performs. The trial to be classified is pre-processed and the WPD coefficient features are extracted. Features corresponding to the previously obtained feature indices are then selected and classified using the 3-layer neural network having previously obtained network parameters.

The proposed methodology is graphically represented in the following figure.

Figure 3.40 Proposed BCI methodology

3.6.2 Neural Network Training Algorithm

The training of the neural network requires following stages.

1. Randomly initialize non-symmetric weight matrices.
2. Implement forward propagation to obtain prediction for each trial in the training set.
3. Implement cost function to calculate costs using predictions and actual clues.
4. Implement back propagation to compute partial derivatives.
5. Gradient checking (optional at the initial training only)
6. Use optimization algorithm to optimize weight matrices such that the cost is minimum.

The designed algorithm is represented graphically in the below figure.

Figure 3.41 Neural Network Training Algorithm

3.6.3 Implementation of the Proposed Methodology –Algorithm

The algorithm of the implemented method to predict a single trial is shown in following figure graphically.

Figure 3.42 Prediction algorithm

3.6.4 Implementation of the Proposed Methodology – Application and GUI

We implemented 2 applications to do the prediction for new trials.

- Command generated randomly by the app

In this application for each trial the subject is advised to relax for 5 seconds and at the end of the 5 seconds, a randomly generated motor imagery command is displayed. The following 3 seconds the subject should perform the given motor imagery task. At the end of this 3 seconds, the acquired signal is classified using the trained BCI and the feedback is given whether the prediction and the original command are the same. This procedure is done in a loop of 10 iterations and the prediction accuracy is given at the end of the 10 predictions.

Figure 3.44 Starting GUI of the random clue generating app

Figure 3.43 Relaxing period of the random clue generating app

Figure 3.45 Motor imagery performing period of the random clue generating app

Figure 3.46 Classifying period of the random clue generating app

Figure 3.47 Correct classification by the random clue generating app

- Command is given by a voice manually

In this application for each trial the subject is advised to relax for 5 seconds and at the end of the 5 seconds, another person gives a motor imagery command by voice. The following 3 seconds the subject should perform the given motor imagery task. At the end of this 3 seconds, the acquired signal is classified using the trained BCI and the prediction is shown. Then the feedback whether the prediction and the original command are the same should be given manually. This procedure can be done in any iterations manually and the cumulative prediction accuracy is given at the end of each predictions.

Figure 3.48 GUI of the manual voice command app

CHAPTER 4

4 RESULTS

4.1 Results Obtained for FFT Features

Table 4.1 Results obtained for FFT features

Feature Extraction Method	Classification Method	Maximum Prediction Accuracy	Average Prediction Accuracy	Average Training Accuracy
AD Instruments Power Lab –Subject 1				
FFT	NN	76%	69%	98%
FFT	DNN	67%	61%	99%

4.2 Results Obtained for Neural Network

Table 4.2 Results obtained for Neural Network

Feature Extraction Method	Feature Selection Method	Maximum Prediction Accuracy	Average Prediction Accuracy	Average Training Accuracy
g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System – Subject 1				
PSD	-	89.5	85.5	96.4
PSD	NCA	95.5	92.2	99.9
Wavelet	-	100	100	100
g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System – Subject 2				
PSD	-	88.2	81.4	99.8

PSD	NCA	85.2	82.9	89.6
Wavelet	-	100	100	100
AD Instruments Power Lab –Subject 1				
PSD	NCA	76.1	72.7	89.4
Wavelet	-	62.6	60.9	99.7
Wavelet	NCA	82.9	79.6	73.8

4.3 Results Obtained for Deep Neural Network

Table 4.3 Results obtained for Deep Neural Network

Feature Extraction Method	Feature Selection Method	Maximum Prediction Accuracy	Average Prediction Accuracy	Average Training Accuracy
g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System – Subject 1				
PSD	-	86.5	79.0	100
PSD	NCA	88.8	83.2	100
Wavelet	-	100	100	100
g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System – Subject 2				
PSD	-	73.5	64.8	100
PSD	NCA	79.4	66.8	82.1
Wavelet	-	100	100	100
AD Instruments Power Lab –Subject 1				

PSD	NCA	57.7	54.7	55.7
Wavelet	-	61.4	60.7	95.1
Wavelet	NCA	71.1	68.1	75.0

4.4 Results Obtained for Support Vector Machine

Table 4.4 Results obtained for Support Vector Machine

Feature Extraction Method	Feature Selection Method	Maximum Prediction Accuracy	Average Prediction Accuracy	Average Training Accuracy
g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System – Subject 1				
PSD	-	76	74.5	76
PSD	NCA	82.2	80	100
PSD	PCA	80	76.6	94
g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System – Subject 2				
PSD	-	72	70	72.5
PSD	NCA	80	78.4	100
PSD	PCA	76	74.8	89.4
AD Instruments Power Lab –Subject 1				
PSD	NCA	75.8	73.4	78
PSD	-	56	55.2	55.7

PSD	PCA	66	64.6	72
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4.5 Results Obtained for Linear Discriminant Analysis

Table 4.5 Results obtained for Linear Discriminant Analysis

Feature Extraction Method	Feature Selection Method	Maximum Prediction Accuracy	Average Prediction Accuracy	Average Training Accuracy
g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System – Subject 1				
PSD	-	58.4	56	68
PSD	NCA	77.3	74.2	100
PSD	PCA	66.6	64	100
g.EEGsys EEG Acquisition System – Subject 2				
PSD	-	55.6	54	65.9
PSD	NCA	75	73.33	100
PSD	PCA	64	60.8	100
AD Instruments Power Lab –Subject 1				
PSD	NCA	71	73.4	79
PSD	-	51.1	50.5	55.4
PSD	PCA	62.2	61.7	100

Chapter 5

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The accuracies increase with respect to the feature extraction method in the sequence of FFT, PSD and WPD for all classification models. FFT is the frequency distribution of the signal where the time resolution is fully lost during the feature extraction, which leads to a lower accuracy. PSD also carries this drawback but it is the spectral power distribution per unit time which improves the information in the extracted features than the FFT, leading to a better accuracy than FFT. WPD up to 5 levels provide a time and frequency representation which boosts the accuracies. Also compared to DWT, WPD improves frequency resolution, which has led to the better accuracies than the phase 1 of this project.

The use of NCA for feature selection reduces the over-fitting of the classifier, removing noise-related features from the feature set. In the phase 1 of this project the DWT features were selected manually, but in this study, the NCA algorithm is used to select features statistically. Therefore, the use of NCA as the feature selection algorithm has directly boosted the accuracies from the phase 1, which is verified by the obtained classifier accuracies.

From the obtained classification accuracies for different combinations of feature extraction, feature selection and classification model, we can see the significance of 3-layer neural network in basic motor imagery classification for data obtained using both the signal acquisition devices, for both the subjects.

When we compare the performance of 4-layer deep neural network with 3-layer neural network, the accuracies for DNN are approximately similar or below that of 3-layer NN. The lesser accuracies of DNN are due to the over-fitting of the input features and lack of features for the feature selection layer of the DNN. When we consider the combinations where NN and DNN give approximately similar accuracies, the 3-layer NN is preferred considering the lower training time of NN. Therefore, as a whole for this classification purpose 3-layer NN serves better than the 4-layer DNN.

Therefore we conclude following the proposed method of this study, a BCI to correctly classify basic motor imageries can be implemented. However the accuracy of the implemented method is directly depended upon the subject, concentration level, hardware used for the signal acquisition and other environmental factors.

Also during this project we practically experienced that the BCI trained to classify motor imagery can also be successfully used to classify the corresponding motor movement.

Chapter 6

6 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER IMPROVEMENTS

In this implementation we classify between 2 basic motor imageries. This can be initially developed to detect 3 stages including the intermediate stage of not performing a motor imagery task. As well discovering the possibility of identifying finer motor imagery using proposed method. This was limited in this study due to hardware limitations.

The algorithm for Neighborhood Component Analysis (NCA) was relatively time consuming. Therefore a less time consuming algorithm for Neighborhood Component Analysis should be used. [27]

This implementation involves an initial training data set for each subject. As a further improvement an adaptive BCI which learns from feedback provided can be designed.

Expand the EEG database using more subjects for the data acquisition. This could have data obtained from disabled or persons with a difficulty in motor movements as well as subjects representing different age groups, gender, etc.

7 REFERENCES

- [1] E. R. A. M. P. M. K. R. Alireza Ghaemia, "Automatic channel selection in EEG signals for classification of left orright hand movement in Brain Computer Interfaces using improvedbinary gravitation search algorithm," Biomedical Signal Processing and Control, 2016.
- [2] A. S. Jasmin Kevrica, "Comparison of signal decomposition methods in classification of EEGsignals for motor-imagery BCI system," Biomedical Signal Processing and Control, 2016.
- [3] R. A. Jyoti Singh Kirar*, "Composite kernel support vector machine based performance enhancement of brain computer interface in conjunction with spatial filter," Biomedical Signal Processing and Control, 2016.
- [4] I. T. S. D.Hari Krishnaa, "Classification of EEG Motor imagery multi class signals based on Cross Correlation," in International Conference on Computational Modelling and Security, 2016.
- [5] H. W. Y. Z. Siuly, "Detection of motor imagery EEG signals employing Naïve Bayes based learning process," Measurement, 2016.
- [6] Z. S. M. Hamid Mirvaziri, "Improvement of EEG-based motor imagery classification using ringtopology-based particle swarm optimization," Biomedical Signal Processing and Control, 2016.
- [7] Athena Akrami, Soroosh Solhjoo, Ali Motie-Nasrabadi and Mohammed Reza Hashemi-Golpayegani, "EEG-Based Mental Task Classification: Linear and Nonlinear Classification of Movement Imagery", *Proceedings of the 27th Annual Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*, Shanghai, China, September 1-4, 2005.
- [8] Pawel Herman, Girijesh Prasad, Thomas Martin McGinnity and Damien Coyle, "Comparative Analysis of Spectral Approaches to Feature Extraction for EEG-Based Motor Imagery Classification", *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, Vol.16, No.4, August 2008
- [9] Xinyi Yong, Carlo Menon, "EEG Classification of Different Imaginary Movements within the Same Limb", 2015

- [10] Hema C.R., Paulraj M.P., S. Yaacob, A. H. Adom, R Nagarajan, "Motor Imagery Signal Classification for a Four State Brain Machine Interface", 2007
- [11] Roxana Aldea, Monica Fira, "Classifications of Motor Imagery Tasks in Brain Computer Interface Using Linear Discriminant Analysis", 2014
- [12] A.Sivakami, S.Shenbaga Devi, "Analysis Of EEG For Motor Imagery Based Classification Of Hand Activities", 2015
- [13] C. Guan et al., "EEG-Based Strategies to Detect Motor Imagery for Control and Rehabilitation," IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON NEURAL SYSTEMS AND REHABILITATION ENGINEERING, vol. 25, no. 4, 2017.
- [14] Ahmed M. ELbaz et al, "Motor Imagery based Brain Computer Interface using Transform," 2016.
- [15] P. SAIDI, "MOTOR IMAGERY CLASSIFICATION USING SPARSE REPRESENTATION OF EEG SIGNALS," Central Florida, 2015.
- [16] M. J. Jeannerod, Mental imagery in the motor context, *Neuropsychologia* 33(11): 1419-1432, 1995
- [17] W. F. Ganong and K. E. Barrett, Review of medical physiology. New York: New York: McGraw-Hill Medical, 2005, vol 21.
- [18] J. E. Hall, Guyton and Hall textbook of medical physiology.: Elsevier Health Sciences, 2010.
- [19] J. Webster, Medical instrumentation: application and design.: John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [20] Audio, NTi. "How an FFT works". www.nti-audio.com.
- [21] Coifman RR & Wickerhauser MV, 1992. Entropy-Based Algorithms for Best Basis Selection, IEEE Transactions on Information Theory, 38(2).
- [22] Daubechies, I. (1992), Ten lectures on wavelets, SIAM

- [23] A.N. Akansu and Y. Liu, On Signal Decomposition Techniques, (Invited Paper), Optical Engineering Journal, special issue Visual Communications and Image Processing, vol.30, pp. 912-920, July 1991
- [24] T. Gandhi, B. Panigrahi and S. Anand, "A comparative study of wavelet families for EEG signal classification", Neurocomputing, vol. 74, no. 17, pp. 3051-3057, 2011.
- [25] P Stoica & R Moses (2005). "Spectral Analysis of Signals" (*PDF*).
- [26] P Stoica & R Moses (2005). "Spectral Analysis of Signals" (*PDF*).
- [27] W. Yang, K. Wang and W. Zuo, "Fast neighborhood component analysis", Neurocomputing, vol. 83, pp. 31-37, 2012.
- [28] Gtec.at. (2018). g.BCIsys - complete Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) research system for data acquisition, real-time and off-line data analysis. Make state-of-the-art Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) experiments within a few hours!. [online] Available at: <http://www.gtec.at/Products/Complete-Solutions/g.BCIsys-Specs-Features>.
- [29] ADInstruments. (2018). Bio Amps. [online] Available at: <https://www.adinstruments.com/products/bio-amps>.
- [30] ADInstruments. (2018). PowerLab. [online] Available at: <https://www.adinstruments.com/products/powerlab>.
- [31] Electro-cap.com. (2018). Caps - Default. [online] Available at: <http://electro-cap.com/index.cfm/caps/>.
- [32] Openbci.com. (2018). OpenBCI. [online] Available at: <http://openbci.com/community/openbci-crossing-swords-with-motor-imagery>.
- [33] Gtec.at. (2018). g.HIamp. [online] Available at: <http://www.gtec.at/Products/Hardware-and-Accessories/g.HIamp-Specs-Features>.

[34] "Neighborhood Component Analysis (NCA) Feature Selection - MATLAB & Simulink - MathWorks United Kingdom", In.mathworks.com, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://in.mathworks.com/help/stats/neighborhood-component-analysis.html>.